

Using wastewater-based epidemiology to estimate consumption of alcohol and nicotine in major cities of China in 2014 and 2016

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ABSTRACT

Monitoring the use of alcohol and tobacco in the population is important for public health planning and evaluating the efficacy of intervention strategies. The aim of this study was to use wastewater-based epidemiology (WBE) to estimate alcohol and tobacco consumption in a number of major cities across China and compare WBE estimates with other data sources. Daily composite influent wastewater samples were collected from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) across China in 2014 ($n = 53$) and 2016 ($n = 45$). The population-normalized daily consumption estimated by WBE were compared with other data sources where available. The average consumption of alcohol was 8.1 ± 7.0 mL ethanol/person aged 15+/day (EPD) in the investigated cities of 2016 while those involved in 2014 had an average consumption of 4.7 ± 3.0 EPD. The average tobacco consumption was estimated to be 3.7 ± 2.2 cigarettes/person aged 15+/day (CPD) in 2016 and 3.1 ± 1.9 CPD in 2014. The changes in the average consumption in those cities from 2014 to 2016 were supported by the results from a limited number of WWTPs where samples were collected in both years. Consumption of alcohol and tobacco in urban China is at a medium level compared with other countries on a per capita basis. WBE estimates of tobacco consumption were relatively comparable with results of traditional surveys and sales statistics. WBE estimates of alcohol consumption were lower than WHO survey results, probably due to EtS degradation and uncertainty in the EtS excretion factor.

1. Introduction

Alcohol and tobacco are the most widely used recreational substances worldwide (World Health Organisation, 2015; World Health Organization, 2017). Consumption of these two substances contributes considerably to the global burden of diseases and injuries (Gakidou, 2017). China is the world's largest consumer of alcohol and tobacco due to its large population with levels of per capita consumption slightly above the world average. China incurs a substantial health burden as a

consequence: nearly one third of the world's smokers live in China, and approximately one million deaths in China every year are associated with tobacco smoking (Zhang et al., 2011). Recently, smoking prevalence was reported to be gradually decreasing in China (World Health Organization, 2018b), whereas alcohol consumption and alcohol related diseases were increasing (Griswold et al., 2018; Jiang et al., 2015). Therefore, continuing to monitor the consumption of alcohol and tobacco in China is important for tailoring public health policies in order to mitigate the burdens of related diseases.

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Traditional methods for estimating alcohol and tobacco consumption in the population include sales statistics (Black et al., 2011) and population surveys (Bush et al., 1998; World Health Organization, 2000), which provide additional demographic and consumer behaviour information. However, survey methods may not accurately reflect actual consumption levels due to the potential sampling bias of incorrect answers (intentional or unintentional) and non-representativeness of the samples. Wastewater-based epidemiology (WBE) is a complementary tool for monitoring consumption of substances including alcohol and tobacco. The method is based on the systematic collection of wastewater samples at the inlet of wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) and subsequent determination of the concentration of parent and/or metabolites of substances that can then be used to back-calculate consumption rates of target compounds. WBE has been used to monitor alcohol and tobacco consumption in a number of countries, with both temporal and geographical consumption profiles being investigated (Andres-Costa et al., 2016; Castiglioni et al., 2015; Chen et al., 2019; Mackie et al., 2019; Mastroianni et al., 2014; Tschärke et al., 2016; van Wel et al., 2016). In China, alcohol consumption has not been evaluated using WBE, while tobacco consumption estimation has been conducted only in Northeastern China with good agreement with survey results (Zheng et al., 2017).

This study thus aims to estimate the consumption of alcohol and tobacco in a number of large cities across China in 2014 and 2016 using WBE. Small towns and rural areas were not included due to the lack of WWTPs and sampling accessibility. The WBE estimates were then compared with sales statistics and survey reports to obtain a better understanding of the consumption of the two substances in China.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Chemicals and reagents

Analytical standards of ethyl-sulphate (EtS), nicotine (NIC), cotinine (COT), trans-3'-hydroxycotinine (OH-COT), EtS-d5, NIC-d4, COT-d3, OH-COT-d3 were purchased from Sigma Aldrich (Castle Hill, Australia). Liquid chromatography–mass spectrometry grade methanol and acetonitrile were purchased from Merck (Germany). Formic acid was purchased from Fisher Scientific (US). Regenerated cellulose syringe filter (0.45 µm) was purchased from Agilent (Mulgrave, Australia). Water was produced by a MilliQ system (Millipore, 0.22 µm filter, 18.2 MΩ cm⁻¹).

2.2. Wastewater sample collection

Influent wastewater samples were collected from WWTPs across China in 2014 and 2016. Daily composite samples were collected using auto-samplers. Details of the sampling campaigns can be found in Gao et al. (2016) and Du et al. (2019). Specifically for this study, in 2014, 53 samples were collected from 29 WWTPs in 17 cities, and in 2016, 45 samples were collected from 19 WWTPs in 16 cities (Tables S1 and S2). All the WWTPs served the urban area of the city and most cities involved (15 of total 17 in 2014, 13 of 16 in 2016) are the provincial capitals or are under direct administration by the central government. The remaining cities have similar population and economic development status as their provincial capitals. It should be noted that due to logistic reasons, the set of cities participating in the 2014 campaign is different from those participating in 2016, with 6 catchments being sampled in both campaigns. The cities included in this study located across all seven geographical regions of China, which allows for the evaluation of spatial variation of consumptions. We used the Qinling-Huaihe Line as the boundary of Northern and Southern China for comparison purpose (Almond et al., 2009).

2.3. Sample preparation and instrumental analysis

Wastewater samples were acidified to pH 2 on site using 2 M HCl and kept frozen before pre-treatment. Filtration of samples were conducted using regenerated cellulose syringe filters (Agilent, 0.45 µm) and a 1 mL filtered sample was pipetted into a 2 mL amber vial. The alcohol consumption biomarker, EtS, was analysed using a previously reported method (Lai et al., 2018). Briefly, 10 µL of 1 mg/L mass-labelled EtS was added to each 1 mL filtered and acidified wastewater sample. These samples were analysed by liquid chromatography (Shimadzu Nexera HPLC) coupled to tandem mass spectrometer (Sciex, 5500-QTrap®) (LC-MS/MS) in direct injection mode. The mass spectrometer parameters are shown in Table S3. The tobacco consumption biomarkers, COT and OH-COT as well as NIC, were determined by the same LC-MS/MS system in direct injection mode using a method validated by Gao et al. (2018). Mass spectrometer parameters for COT, OH-COT and NIC are shown in Table S4. Concentration of analytes were determined by internal calibration method, e.g. comparing transition intensity ratios between the sample and the calibration curve produced with several calibration standards in the same batch. The performance of the analytical method is provided in Table S5.

2.4. Data analysis

The per capita consumption of alcohol ($Vol_{Alcohol}$) was calculated by Equation (1):

$$Vol_{Alcohol}(\text{ethanol (ml)/person aged 15+/day; EPD}) = \frac{C_{EtS} \times F \times f_{Alcohol}}{R_{15+} \times P \times \rho_{Alcohol}} \quad (1)$$

where C_{EtS} is the concentration of EtS in wastewater (µg/L), F is the daily influent flow (L/d), $f_{Alcohol}$ is the correction factor of EtS after alcohol consumption, $\rho_{Alcohol}$ is the density of alcohol (g/mL). P is the WWTP catchment population (million inhabitants). R_{15+} is the ratio of population aged ≥ 15 years (15+) in the catchment (National Bureau of Statistics, 2015). Detail information is provided in Table S6.

Since COT demonstrated higher in-sewer stability (Banks et al., 2018; Gao et al., 2019), the per capita consumption of nicotine (m_{NIC}) is calculated by Equation (2).

$$m_{NIC}(\text{mg/person/day}) = \frac{C_{COT} \times F \times f_{NIC} \times 1000}{P} \quad (2)$$

where C_{COT} is the concentration in wastewater (µg/L) and f_{NIC} is the correction factor of COT after tobacco smoking. We also back calculated NIC consumption using OH-COT and both COT and OH-COT, respectively (Table S7). In China, tobacco smoking is the predominant source of nicotine consumption since the contribution from other nicotine containing products (such as electronic cigarettes and nicotine replacement therapy products) are negligible due to their high cost (Gravelly et al., 2014; Lam et al., 2005). The daily tobacco consumption (n_D) is calculated from nicotine consumption by using Equation (3).

$$n_D(\text{cigarettes/person aged 15+/day; CPD}) = \frac{m_{NIC}}{D \times Y \times R_{15+}} \quad (3)$$

where D is the content of NIC in an average cigarette (mg/cigarette), Y the average yield of NIC uptake during smoking (%) (Charles et al., 2009; Wang et al., 2016).

For accessing uncertainty and sensitivity of the estimation, Monte Carlo simulation (Oracle Crystal Ball software, Version 7.3.1) was used (Wang et al., 2016). The Monte Carlo simulation was based on repeated random sampling of the probability distributions defined for the principal factors of variation of each input parameter (Table S8). Graphpad Prism 7 and Origin 2018 were used for statistical analysis and graphing.

Table 1
Biomarker concentration and estimated alcohol and tobacco consumption in China.

WWTPs-City	COT (µg/L)	EtS (µg/L)	COT/OH-COT	NIC consumption (mg/person/day)	Tobacco consumption (CPD)	Alcohol consumption (EPD)
29 WWTPs across China in 2014	1.6 ± 0.7	3.1 ± 1.4	0.8 ± 0.1	1.6 ± 0.9	3.1 ± 1.9	4.7 ± 3.0
19 WWTPs across China in 2016	2.3 ± 1.3	5.7 ± 4.0	0.5 ± 0.1	1.9 ± 1.1	3.7 ± 2.2	8.1 ± 7.0

COT/OH-COT is the concentration ratio of COT and OH-COT in the same sample; CPD = cigarettes/person aged 15+ /day; EPD = ethanol (mL)/person aged 15+ /day; data presented in average ± standard deviation.

3. Results

3.1. Occurrences of consumption biomarkers in wastewater

Biomarkers of alcohol and tobacco consumption were detected in all samples. Concentration of alcohol metabolite EtS ranged from 0.5 µg/L (WH-1) to 12.1 µg/L (CD-1) with a median of 3.5 µg/L. Concentration of COT ranged from 0.4 (WH-1) to 4.7 µg/L (LZ-2). The concentration of OH-COT was higher than COT in most samples, ranging from 0.5 (WH-1) to 10.8 µg/L (LZ-2) (Table S7).(see Table 1)

3.2. Spatial variation

Overall, the consumption of both alcohol and tobacco in Northern China was higher than in Southern China (Fig. 1). In 2014, the lowest alcohol consumption was observed in WH-1 with 1.3 EPD and the

highest level was observed in JN-1 with 14.4 EPD. The alcohol consumption in cities located in Northern China (6.1 ± 3.3 EPD) was significantly higher than that in Southern China (3.0 ± 1.3 EPD) in 2014 (t test, p = 0.001). However, this geographical difference was much smaller in 2016, as 8.1 ± 3.4 EPD in Northern China and 7.0 ± 6.9 EPD in Southern China (t test, p = 0.23).

In 2014, Northern China had significantly higher tobacco consumption than Southern China (t test, p = 0.002) with the CPD values of 3.9 ± 2.1 and 2.0 ± 0.8, respectively. This geographical difference is similar in 2016 with significantly higher (t test, p = 0.009) tobacco consumption in Northern China (4.5 ± 1.7 CPD) than in Southern China (3.2 ± 2.3 CPD). The lowest tobacco consumption was found at GY-1 (Guiyang) in the South with 1.0 CPD, while YC-1 (Yinchuan) in the North had the highest tobacco consumption of 8.4 CPD in 2014.

3.3. Variations between 2014 and 2016

The average alcohol consumption in the urban catchments included in this study was significantly higher in 2016 (8.1 ± 7.0 EPD) than in 2014 (4.7 ± 3.0 EPD) (t test, p = 0.002). The level of increase observed by WBE is much higher than has been reported by traditional statistics (Statista, 2018; World Health Organisation, 2014). Unlike the observed increase of alcohol consumption, tobacco consumption across urban areas in China in 2016 (3.7 ± 2.2 CPD) was slightly higher than 2014 (3.1 ± 1.9 CPD) (t test, p > 0.05).

In the six WWTPs where samples were obtained in both 2014 and 2016, we observed some level of increases of alcohol and tobacco consumption. However, the tobacco consumption between 2014 and 2016 is statistically non-significant (p > 0.05) (Fig. 2).

4. Discussion

4.1. Consumption comparison between Northern and Southern China

Our results indicated that consumption of both alcohol and tobacco in Northern China was higher than in Southern China. The geographical pattern of alcohol consumption in this study is in good agreement with traditional survey results, which also reported higher drinking rates in Northern China (Cochrane et al., 2003). Normally, colder weather and fewer sunlight hours will increase alcohol consumption (Ventura-Cots et al., 2019). Thus, the difference in climate between Northern and Southern China is one of the reasons for the geographical pattern of alcohol consumption. In addition, higher alcohol consumption is also reported in rural areas compared to urban areas in Northern China (Zhou et al., 2011).

A recent WHO report on tobacco consumption in 14 Chinese cities in 2013–2014 showed that tobacco consumption in Northern China (3.25 CPD) was higher than in Southern China (2.39 CPD) (World Health Organization, 2015). These WHO estimates were similar to our WBE-based results in 2014. The higher tobacco consumption in the North of China could be attributed to cultural and habitual factors as well as economic factor. A previous study has suggested that smoking rates generally declines with better economic status (Chaloupka and Warner, 2000). As a guide to economic prosperity between Northern and Southern China, Northern China contributed 42% of total Chinese GDP while 58% was contributed by Southern China in 2014.

Fig. 1. Consumption of alcohol and tobacco in different catchments in China in 2014 and 2016. CPD = cigarettes/person aged 15+ /day; EPD = ethanol (mL)/person aged 15+ /day.

Fig. 2. Variation of alcohol and tobacco consumption in catchments with samples collected in both 2014 and 2016 (In 2014, $n = 2$ for all WWTPs except SZ-2 which $n = 3$. In 2016, $n = 2$ for SH-2, SZ-2, XM-2 and BJ-1, $n = 3$ for HZ-2 and SZ-2) CPD = cigarettes/person aged 15+ /day; EPD = ethanol (mL)/person aged 15+ /day.

4.2. Comparison between WBE estimation and other data sources

The average alcohol consumption in large cities across China measured in this study (4.7 and 8.1 EPD in 2014 and 2016, respectively) was much lower compared with the WHO survey report for 2015–2017, which reported an estimate of approximately 19.7 EPD (World Health Organization, 2018a). Lower alcohol consumption estimated by WBE studies compared to traditional surveys was also reported in other WBE studies. Twelve out of 14 WBE studies reported lower alcohol consumption levels while 2 studies showed similar consumption levels (Table 2). A consistent underestimation of alcohol consumption by WBE compared to sales data was also observed in a 6-year monitoring study (Zheng et al., 2020). The relatively lower WBE estimates could be attributed to the following factors: (i) the WHO report covered both urban and rural areas while most WBE studies only cover more urbanized areas, and rural areas were reported to have higher alcohol consumption than urban areas (Fang et al., 2018; Millwood et al., 2013); (ii). The degradation of EtS during sewer transport and uncertainty around the EtS excretion factor may have caused an underestimate of alcohol consumption; and (iii) Uncertainty related to standardisation of alcohol products could also lead to the discrepancy in consumption rates between WBE studies and self-reported questionnaire surveys (Zheng et al., 2019).

The average tobacco consumption in China estimated by WBE in this study (3.1 and 3.7 CPD in 2014 and 2016) was similar to the Chinese adult tobacco survey in 2015 (3.6 CPD) (CCDC, 2015). However, our estimation is lower than the value of 4.7 CPD reported by the 2015 Global Adult Tobacco Survey (GATS, 2015) and the value of 5.6 CPD estimated from sales statistics extracted from the 2016 national tobacco report (CNTC, 2017).

Tobacco consumption in some of the cities involved in our study were also evaluated by a WHO survey conducted in 2014, which provides the unique opportunity to compare WBE results with survey data (World Health Organization, 2015). Five out of seven cities showed good agreement with < 20% difference (Fig. 3). In HRB, a much higher tobacco consumption was reported by WHO survey whereas in HZ, the WBE estimate was higher than the WHO value. For HRB, the lower WBE estimates may be due to the investigated WWTP catchment only covering 0.55 million of the urban population, while there were 4.9 million people in both suburban and rural areas (of the 9.5 million total population in HRB) covered by the WHO report. For HZ, the WBE sampling covered more than half of the population, so the lower WHO estimates may be attributed to the sampling bias in the WHO survey, a factor which warrants further evaluation.

4.3. Comparison of WBE results with other countries

Alcohol consumption in major cities across China estimated by WBE in this study was lower than those in other countries including Australia (7–24 EPD), Spain (18 EPD), Belgium (15.3 EPD), the United States (6–93 EPD), as well as the values from 20 cities in 11 countries (6.4–44.3 EPD, median 20.9 EPD) (Boogaerts et al., 2016; Chen et al., 2019; Lai et al., 2018; Mastroianni et al., 2014; Ryu et al., 2016) (Table 2). The lower alcohol consumption observed in China is also supported by the WHO survey report (World Health Organisation, 2014). The lower alcohol consumption in Chinese cities compared to those in other countries such as Australia and Belgium could be partially attributed to the lower percentage of regular consumers of alcohol (17.3% in China, 52.4% in Australia, and 41.7% in Belgium).

As the nicotine content in cigarettes vary, using the per capita nicotine consumption for comparison is more useful than using the number of cigarettes smoked, especially for comparison between different cultures and demographics (Wayne et al., 2006). Since we noted that different excretion factors for nicotine biomarkers were used in different WBE studies, a standard conversion of nicotine consumption was used for comparison (Table 3). The nicotine consumption in China (1.5 ± 0.9 mg/person/day in 2014 and 1.8 ± 1.1 mg/person/day in 2016) was similar to Australia (1.7 ± 0.6 mg/person/day) and Spain (1.7 mg/person/day), but much lower than Italy (3.4 mg/person/day), the United States (2.7 mg/person/day) and Portugal (2.6 mg/person/day) (Castiglioni et al., 2015; Chen et al., 2019; Lai et al., 2018; Lopes et al., 2014; Rodriguez-Alvarez et al., 2014b).

4.4. Uncertainties and limitations

In this study, we have used the two stability benchmarking chemicals, acesulfame – a stable biomarker and paracetamol – an unstable one, to evaluate the potential degradation of the consumption biomarkers of alcohol and tobacco during transport and preservation in this study (Gao et al., 2017; Gao et al., 2019; O'Brien et al., 2017). Our data showed that degradation did not have a significant effect on our samples (Table S9).

The general uncertainties for WBE applications and specifically for alcohol and tobacco biomarkers apply for this study, such as the instrumental measurement and real-time population estimation (Castiglioni et al., 2013; Zheng et al., 2019). For alcohol consumption, excretion factor of EtS, ranging from 0.010 to 0.016%, is probably the largest contributor to the overall uncertainty. For tobacco consumption, the uncertainty of D , large variance of nicotine amongst each cigarette (0.4–1.2 mg) in different brands was observed and attributed to smokers' habits (Zheng et al., 2017). Meanwhile excretion of NIC to COT

Table 2
Comparison of alcohol consumption in different countries.

City, Country	Year	WWTPs(n)	Population	Alcohol consumption range (average) (EPD)	Excretion factor used (%)	Reference	Alcohol consumption in 2015–2017 reported by WHO (national average, EPD)
Barcelona, Spain	2013–2015	1	998,846–992,301 (R15 +)	7–31 (17.6)	0.01	(Mastroianni et al., 2017)	27.4
Lesvos, Greece	2015	3	1,250–26,000 (All)	1.7–11.2 (5.4)	0.012	(Gatidou et al., 2016)	28.5
Galicia, Spain	2012	1	100,000 (All)	9.3–23.5 (16.3)	0.010–0.016	(Rodríguez-Alvarez et al., 2014a)	28.4*
Oslo, Norway	2009	1	500,000 (All)	12.4–19.8	0.010–0.016	(Reid et al., 2011)	24.6*
Santiago de Compostela, Spain	2012–2014	1	136,500 (All)	3.8–22.6 (13.6)	0.012	(Rodríguez-Alvarez et al., 2015)	27.4
Milan, Italy	2012–2014	1	1,150,000 (All)	3.2–10.5 (5.1)	0.012	(Ryu et al., 2016)	20.8
20 Cities in 11 countries	2014–2015	23	34,495–1,500,000 (All)	6.4–44.3	0.012	(Mastroianni et al., 2014)	27.4
Barcelona, Spain	-	1	1,157,000 (R15 +)	12–27 (18)	0.011	(Andres-Costa et al., 2016)	27.4
Valencia, Spain	2014	3	Sum of 1,500,000 (R15 +)	1.07–56.1	0.010–0.016	(Baz-Lomba et al., 2016)	27.4
8 European cities	2015	8	Sum of 5,000,000 (All)	2.1–9.6 (5.1)	-	(Lai et al., 2018)	29.0
Australia	2014–2015	18	Sum of 10,800,000 (All)	(7–24)	0.012	(Nguyen et al., 2018)	No data
Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam	2015	2	Sum of 54,5830 (All)	(2.7–3.9)	0.012	(Boogaerts et al., 2016)	32.2
Belgium	2013–2015	8	78,441–953,987 (R15 +)	5.29–33.3 (15.3)	0.012	(Chen et al., 2019)	26.8
3 cities in the U.S.	2015–2016	3	53,000–125,000 (R15 +)	5.7–92.9 (29.4)	0.012	(Zheng et al., 2020)	29.0
1 city in Australia	2012–2017	1	87,124–109,294 (All)	15.7–25.3 (17.6)	0.012	This study	19.7
17 cities in China	2014	29	200,000–3,450,000 (R15 +)	1.34–14.4 (4.8)	0.012	This study	19.7
21 cities in China	2016	19	107,600–3,338,500 (R15 +)	1.38–20.8 (7.5)	0.012	This study	19.7

* Data reported during 2009–2011.

Fig. 3. Comparison of tobacco consumption between WBE estimates and WHO results in 2014; (n = 5 for SZ, 4 for LY and SY, 3 for BJ and HZ, 2 for HRB and LZ for WBE).

could be different due to influences of enzymes, age, gender, diet and medications, which can contribute to uncertainty in the excretion factor (Hukkanen et al., 2005).

Using Monte Carlo simulation, the average alcohol consumption across China in 2014 and 2016 was estimated to be 4.3 EPD (95% CI: 3.4–5.3 EPD) and 8.2 EPD (95% CI: 6.0–11.9), respectively. The average tobacco consumption estimates were 3.4 CPD (95%CI: 2.0–5.8 CPD) in 2014 and 4.8 CPD (95%CI: 3.0–8.0 CPD) in 2016 (Fig. S1). The Monte Carlo simulation results were in good agreement with the estimation based on the mean value of input parameters used above.

Although our study provided geographical profiles of alcohol and tobacco consumption across China, we acknowledge some limitations. First, the population size of the catchments included in this study were from the best estimates provided by the WWTP managers and the Census data. Such population counts have unknown uncertainty due to catchment development and population migration. Second, the catchments investigated in 2016 were not exactly the same as those in 2014, so the national average comparison between 2014 and 2016 may be affected by geographical differences. Third, due to the lack of detailed understanding of the catchment sewer profile (HRT distribution, A/V distribution), we could not compensate the in-sewer degradation of biomarkers in our back-calculation. Fourth, due to logistical reasons, a limited number of samples (1–3) were provided by the WWTPs each year. This adds to the uncertainty in the yearly consumption estimation. Future campaigns should carefully evaluate the number of samples required for annual estimation of alcohol and tobacco consumption, similar to evaluations made in relation to other substances (e.g. Ort et al., 2014; Humphries et al., 2016). Furthermore, like many other WBE studies, the consumption estimates using WBE do not include the demographic characteristics of the population such as age distribution, consumption frequency and prevalence of heavy users. Therefore, strict interpretation of our results should consider the uncertainties and limitations outlined above.

5. Conclusion

According to the results of this study, the average alcohol consumption in urban China in 2016 was higher than that in 2014. Tobacco consumption showed no statistical difference between the two years. Northern China had higher level of alcohol and tobacco consumption compared to Southern China. Overall, the WBE estimates for alcohol consumption in China were lower than those reported in the WHO surveys, but the geographical difference between Northern and Southern China was well reflected in both approaches. Temporal and geographical profiles of tobacco consumption derived from WBE showed relatively good agreement with survey reports and sales

Table 3
Comparison of nicotine and tobacco consumption in different countries.

City, Country	Year	WWTPs (n)	Population	Nicotine consumption (average) (mg/day/person)	Tobacco consumption (average) (CPD)	Excrete factor used (%)	Reference	Standard conversion using excretion factor (COT:32.3%, OHCOT: 43.4%)
Jilin, China	2016	10	61,300–1,270,000 (All)	1.0–6.1	1.82–11.7	COT: 32.3	(Zheng et al., 2017)	1.0–6.1
Dalian, China	2015	11	65,000–350,000 (All)	1.6–2.4 (2.0)	(3)	COT: 32.3 OH-COT: 43.4	(Wang et al., 2016)	1.6–2.4 (2.0)
Lier, Belgium	2014	1	30,600(All)	5.6	(4.5)	–	(van Wel et al., 2016)	
8 Italian cities	2012	–	79,926–1,201,490 (R15 +)	2.2–4.5 (3.5)	1.8–3.4	COT: 30 OH-COT: 44	(Castiglioni et al., 2015)	2.2–4.4 (3.4)
Lisbon, Portugal	2011	3	–	4.9–12.9 (5.9)	–	COT:14.1	(Lopes et al., 2014)	2.1–5.6 (2.6)
Australia	2014–2015	18	Sum of 10,800,000 (All)	0.75–3.02 (1.8)	0.85–3.4	COT: 28.05 OH-COT: 45.23	(Lai et al., 2018)	0.7–2.9 (1.7)
Galicia, Spain	2012–2014	1	130,000 (All)	0.9–2.6 (1.8)	–	COT: 27 OH-COT: 44.5	(Rodriguez-Alvarez et al., 2014a)	0.9–2.5 (1.7)
Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam	2015	2	Sum of 545,830 (All)	1.1–1.3	–	COT and OHCOT:13	(Nguyen et al., 2018)	0.4–0.5
Czech Republic	2014	2	120,000–1,300,000 (All)	3.6–4.3	4.5–5.4	COT:14.1	(Mackuřak et al., 2015)	1.6–1.9
Slovak Republic	2014	5	35,000–450,000 (All)	2.2–8.0	2.8–10.1	COT:14.1		1.0–3.5
3 cities in the U.S.	2015–2016	3	53,000–125,000 (All)	0.8–4.1 (2.7)	–	COT + OH-COT:74	(Chen et al., 2019)	1.7–8.7
1 city in Australia	2010–2017	1	87,000–10,9000 (All)	1.9–2.3	2.5–3.5	COT:32	(Mackie et al., 2019)	2.5–3.5
17 cities in China	2014	29	200,000–3,450,000 (R15 +)	0.5–3.9	1.0–8.4	COT:32.3	This study	0.5–3.9
21 cities in China	2016	19	107,600–3,338,500 (R15 +)	0.6–4.5	1.1–8.7	COT:32.3	This study	0.6–4.5

statistics but could be obtained in a shorter timeframe. More efforts are required to reduce the uncertainties related to WBE estimation to improve the accuracy of the consumption estimates.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Jianfa Gao: Data curation, Formal analysis, Methodology, Software, Writing - original draft. **Qiuda Zheng:** Formal analysis, Investigation, Visualization, Writing - original draft. **Foon Yin Lai:** Methodology, Validation, Writing - review & editing. **Coral Gartner:** Investigation, Writing - review & editing. **Peng Du:** Project administration, Resources, Writing - review & editing. **Yuan Ren:** Resources, Writing - review & editing. **Xiqing Li:** Funding acquisition, Writing - review & editing. **Degao Wang:** Writing - review & editing. **Jochen F. Mueller:** Funding acquisition, Writing - review & editing. **Phong K. Thai:** Conceptualization, Supervision, Validation, Writing - review & editing.

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Appendix A. Supplementary material

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